

Relativistic Charged Particle in a Magnetic/Electric Fields and Lorentz Invariants

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Maxwell's electromagnetic equations were obtained before special relativity was developed as was Lorentz's force equation for a charged particle in electric and magnetic fields. As a result, a Lagrangian for a charged particle was written for the nonrelativistic situation. In particular following (1), we see that kinetic energy for a noncharged particle (nonrelativistic) is $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$, but (1) uses the Lorentz force to obtain $-q(\phi - \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{A})$ where q is the particle charge, ϕ the electric potential and \mathbf{A} the magnetic vector potential. This form is carried over into the relativistic case (described in (1)) and called a potential.

The form, $q(\phi - \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{A})$ is a Lorentz invariant (if one uses (dx, cdt) as one vector) from special relativity, while $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ is not. As a result, a special relativistic form, derived without using special relativity explicitly is combined with an explicit nonrelativistic form $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$.

Here we suggest that both terms should follow from relativistic considerations for consistency. In (2), we suggested that one may obtain the form $-EE + pcpc = momocccc$ ((1)) by using information considerations. This in turn led to a corresponding Lorentz transformation. In (3) we argued that m_0 should appear in a linear form in ((1)) so that E and p are additive. We suggest that from these ideas, one should consider $q\phi$ as a form of energy like m_0 and it should follow the same transformation rules as m_0 . For consistency, there exists a momentum if one views the particle from a moving frame, and one may suggest a momentum field \mathbf{A} linked with ϕ as a parallel. Following these arguments, one obtains the Lagrangian for a charged particle in a special relativistic manner such that the Lorentz invariants $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ with $-q\phi + \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{A}$ added yield the action, just as $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ for a free particle yields the action, which in turn is Lt . Here one may generalize to Ldt .

The Emergence of Energy and Momentum for a Free Particle from Frame Reference Points and Information

In (2), we argued that one may consider a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at some time t_0 . If this particle is viewed from a frame moving with constant $-v$ or $+v$, the particle will be seen to move at v or $-v$, but physically this must be equivalent to the particle at rest. As a result, we argue that the physical information is unchanged. For the rest frame, there is no preferred direction, but for v or $-v$ by themselves there is. There is no reason to choose one over the other, so we proposed creating a matrix using the row vectors $(x,0)$ and $(0,bt)$ where b is a constant (with velocity units) which converts t into a distance. The two vectors are orthogonal following the convection $(x,0,0)$, $(0,y,0)$, $(0,0,z)$ in 3-space. We then multiplied this matrix by $m(v)/t$, where $m(v=0)=m_0$. In other words, we allow for the possibility that the mass seen from the moving frame is not the same number as that seen in the rest frame.

We then multiplied such a matrix for v by one for $-v$ and equated the trace of this to the trace of the matrix created by the row vectors $(0,0)$, $(0, m_0)$ multiplied by itself. This yields:

$$mm - mmv/bb = momo \quad ((2))$$

Thus, one has the emergence to two new quantities which we call energy and momentum, i.e.

$$\text{Energy} = m \gamma c^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{momentum} = m \gamma v \quad ((3))$$

B is a constant which is unknown. In order to determine it, we consider a photon and suggest it should also have energy and momentum. Using the dispersion relation $v = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$ and calling frequency proportional to energy and wavelength to $1/p$ one obtains $E = pc$ or $E^2 = p^2 c^2$. This matches ((3)) with $m_0 = 0$. As a result, the concepts of energy and momentum do not simply hold for a particle with rest mass, but also for other energy forms, such as a photon.

The Creation of Lorentz Invariants

((2)) written as $E^2 - pc^2 = m_0^2 c^4$ may be considered to be a special dot product of the vectors (pc, E) using a minus sign for the fourth component. Furthermore, one has $(0, m_0 c)$ mapping into (pc, E) and so one may create a Lorentz transformation to describe this. Given that (x, ct) and (pc, E) are two different Lorentz vectors one may take their dot product to create the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + px \quad ((4))$$

In (3), we argued that m_0 should be used in ((2)) even though one could in principle replace m_0 with $f(m_0)$, where f is an arbitrary function. The reason for this is additivity of both m_0 and E .

At first $-Et + px$ may seem like an arbitrary Lorentz invariant, but it is in fact the classical action Lt for a free particle, where L is called the Lagrangian in nonrelativistic theory. Thus:

$$\text{Action} = Lt = -Et + px = -m_0 c^2 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((5))$$

In other words, the classical action is a Lorentz invariant. We suggest that this is linked with the idea of physical information not fundamentally changing if a system is viewed from a frame moving with constant velocity.

The Case of a Charged Particle in Electric and Magnetic Fields

The problem of a charged particle moving in electric and magnetic fields was solved nonrelativistically using Maxwell's electromagnetic equations and Lorentz force equation before special relativity was developed. In particular, a nonrelativistic free particle has a kinetic energy of $p^2/2m_0$ (no E, B fields) where $p = m_0 v$.

In order to find the potential which applies in the case of a nonrelativistic particle moving in electric and magnetic fields, (1) suggests using Lorentz force and states that the result is:

$$V(x) = q(\phi - v \cdot A) \quad \text{where } q \text{ is charge, } \phi, \text{ the electric potential and } A \text{ the magnetic vector potential} \quad ((6))$$

We point out that ((6)) is of the form of a Lorentz invariant if one factors out dt and that q phi represents energy in the same manner that mo or mo/sqrt(1-vv/cc) does.

As a result, we argue that the classical action for a free particle (no E,B fields) is a Lorentz invariant and ((6)), the potential, the same type of Lorentz invariant. Here we use (dx, cdt) as the spatial vector.

Given that the classical action for a free particle is -Edt+pdx and E is linear because energies add, then q phi should add to E in principle. The same argument exists for momentum. Thus, we suggest that one has for a particle in an electric and magnetic field:

$$-(mcc + q \phi) + c (p(\text{particle}) dx + A(x)dx) \text{ as the action (in 1-dimension) ((7))}$$

In three dimensions, one uses the regular dot product.

Thus, using special relativistic considerations and treating mass energy mcc on the same footing as q phi, one is forced to consider the two vectors (p(particle)c, mcc) and (A, phi) as additive and behaving in the same manner. Given that a photon transforms like a particle with rest mass under a Lorentz transformation (an argument used to set the constant b to c, the speed of light in a vacuum), there is no reason that other energy entities, such as A vector and phi cannot transform in the same manner as well.

As a result, we suggest the action (or rather L dt) of a particle with or without electric and magnetic fields follows from Lorentz invariance.

The Case of Momentum

The above arguments suggest that there are now two momenta in the physical scenario, namely the particle momentum and the vector magnetic potential A. The two add linearly, so one may describe the system in terms of single combined momentum which is what occurs when one uses the classical definition::

$$\text{Momentum} = dL/dv \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{With } p(\text{particle})=p_1 \text{ one has: } L = -E + p_1 v - q (\phi) + qv A \text{ so: } p = p_1 + qA$$

Momentum is now the combined result, not the particle momentum. If one uses the classical rule:

$$H = pv - L \quad ((9)) \text{ then: } H = E + q \phi \text{ where } E = \sqrt{(momocccc + p_1 p_1 cc)}$$

Quantum Mechanical Considerations

In (4), we argued that the quantum mechanical form exp(ipx) is an eigenfunction of the operator d/dx which describes motion in space in terms of a conserved quantity, namely p. As a

result, if one has both p_1 and $-qA$ as momentum pieces, it seems the full form $\exp(ipx)$ should be used in the region for which there exists $A(x)$. Actually, the full form is: $\exp(i \int p dx)$. If one has no ϕ and an vector potential $A(x)$ which does not create a B field which acts as a force on the particle, then p_1 is a constant and one has:

$\exp(i p_1 x + \int_{x_1,x} A(x) dx)$ ((10)) where p_1 is the particle momentum

This shows that motion which accounts for conservation of total momentum leads to a phase shift. This is called the Bohm-Aharonov effect.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that one may use the notion of information to argue that there must be a mathematical expression linking the picture of a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=0$, i.e. a particle at rest, with this particle seen from frames moving with constant $-v, v$. The rest mass has no motion, but v and $-v$ have direction so we created in (2) two matrices (described above) with v and $-v$ and multiplied them after multiplying by the constant $m(v)/t$. We took the trace of this product and equated it to the trace of the product of the matrix formed by the row vectors $(0,0)$ $(0,m_0)$, multiplied by itself. This led to $-EE + pcpc = m_0 m_0 c^2 c^2$ ((1)), where c is a constant which we argued was the speed of light in a vacuum. We argued in (3) that m_0 instead of $f(m_0)$ (f being an arbitrary function) should be used for additivity reasons for m_0 and E . This leads to the notion of a vector (pc, E) , but also one for (x, ct) with ((1)) being a dot product $(1, -1)$. Thus, one may take the dot product of (x, ct) and (pc, E) to find an equation containing x, t and energy. This happens to be the classical action.

In (1), a charged particle moving in electric and magnetic fields is described as being acted upon by a potential $q(\phi - v \cdot A)$, where q is charge, ϕ the electric potential and A the magnetic vector one. This result is obtained through considerations of the Lorentz force equation which was obtained before special relativity was known.

We propose a strictly special relativistic solution to the problem. We suggest that ϕ represents energy just like m_0 and so should behave in the same way. In fact, we suggest that (A, ϕ) is a vector like (pc, E) . This suggests creating the Lorentz invariant using the vectors: (dx, cdt) and $(p_1 c + qA, E + q\phi)$ which should then be the Lagrangian for a particle in an electric and magnetic fields if one factors out dt .

References

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